

CERTIFICATE

◆◆◆ THIS CERTIFICATE IS PROUDLY PRESENTED TO ◆◆◆

O'ZBEKISTONDA TA'LIM-TARBIYA JARAYONIGA INNOVATSION
YONDASHUVLAR.MUAMMO VA YECHIMLAR MAVZUSIDA RESPUBLIKA
ILMIY ONLINE KONFERENSIYASIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

Usmanov S

ORGANIZATIONAL AND METHODOLOGICAL PRINCIPLES OF

DEVELOPMENT OF ECOLOGICAL COMPETENCE IN STUDENTS

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

TAQDIRLANADI

zenodo

2023/YANVAR

